

DIAGNOSTIC CORE RESOURCES

Viral Quality Assurance Panels (VQAS): The core will produce “native” Washington strain SARS-CoV-2 as well as key circulating variants requested or chosen by our Variants Board (VB).

Availability of Standards:

- **Phase 1 (March 2021):** WA1 will first be available as frozen stock of UV inactivated virus which will be shipped on request to awardees frozen in standard buffer at a high known titer, or aliquoted into the biospecimen of choice.
- **Phase 2 (~April 2021):** We will make available the first quality assurance panel containing labeled viral stock as well as blinded specimens containing native virus, at least a single variant strain, a non-SARS-CoV-2 coronavirus and 1-2 respiratory virus selected from the FDA EUA guidance. These will include heat and UV inactivated virus and potentially irradiated or chemically treated virus on a case-by-case basis.
- **Phase 3 (~June 2021):** Extended offerings of VQAs with circulating variants and distractor pathogens recommended for EUA with various inactivation methods.
- **Phase 4 (~Aug 2021):** Potential for on demand viral synthesis and limited affinity

molecule requests.

Diagnostic Development Guidance: Diagnostic development guidance will be provided. This will include individual support on request, office ours and Q&A services as well as FAQs.

Usability Guidance: We will provide usability and human factors resources on the web portal as well as access to usability experts and toolkits.

Benchmarking Services: All viral standards will be benchmarked across common platforms to calibrate viral copy number and antigen concentration. Benchmarking requests will be handled on a case-by-case basic depending on need.

Vendor Services: We recognize there is significant competition for resources and vender services. We will help with advice on vendors and potential synergistic services from other RAD_x programs.

News Services: We will provide frequent news and updates relevant to test development, variants and emerging diagnostic technologies.

Toolkits: We will provide access to external tools and toolkits to support diagnostic development and testing. We will provide hosted LIMS, web tools to track variants and

diagnostic challenges as well as tools to integrate new tests with others for diagnostic decision making.